

Yoga philosophy and its significance in modern life

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The Yoga philosophy is an invaluable gift of the sage Patanjali. Yoga is an important method of realizing the spiritual truth. The aim of yoga is to realize the existence of spirit, through the control of the body, senses and mind. A man cannot realize spiritual truths so long as his mind is impure and unsettled. For the purification of the mind, yoga gives us the Eightfold Path of Discipline, which is also known as Astanga Yoga. The practice of Yoga is the best way of self-purification. With the development of science and information technology, modern lifestyle has lost the harmony in the mind-body relationship. There is a requirement for making people aware about the benefits of practicing yoga. This study will analyse the significance of yoga in our daily life for a healthy lifestyle. Yoga is very beneficial for improving the quality of life. Yoga helps in achieving a peaceful mind and body and uplifts the spirit.

Keywords: spirit, realization, life.